

PRODUCTION OF PANCREATIC LIPASE INHIBITORS BY ENDOPHYTIC FUNGI UNDER CONDITIONS OF SUBMERGED AND SOLID-PHASE FERMENTATION

Yuldosheva M.M.

Lecturer, Department of Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Alfraganus University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14548983>

Abstract. *It is important to suggest that the prevalence of obesity continues to increase across all age groups and populations worldwide. Obesity is a complex disease that increases the risk of health disorders such as diabetes, metabolic syndrome, heart disease, cancer and stroke. Mortality due to obesity is very high; it is the fifth leading cause of death worldwide.*

Keywords: *obesity, anti-obesity drug, blood pressure, synthetic gastrointestinal, bioactive substances.*

Definitely, prevention and treatment of obesity are critical for health systems that aim to reduce the prevalence of obesity, overweight and related complications [4]. Physicians and other healthcare professionals can treat obesity in a variety of ways, including dietary regimens, exercise, and pharmacotherapy. The currently used anti-obesity drug, orlistat is a synthetic gastrointestinal lipase inhibitor that limits the hydrolysis of triglycerides to reduce the subsequent absorption of monoglycerides and free fatty acids in the intestine [5].

However, this anti-obesity drug causes serious side effects including insomnia, headache, dry mouth, constipation, high blood pressure and heart attack [6,7]. Therefore, research on medicinal plants with anti-obesity activity has become a subject of increased interest due to their natural origin, low cost and limited side effects [8-10].

Since the use of medicinal plants as a source of bioactive compounds leads to a decrease in natural diversity, an alternative source of bioactive substances and ensuring the necessary production of these compounds while preserving biodiversity and ecosystems is needed, which can be achieved through endophytic fungal biotechnology [11].

Moreover, endophytic fungi, being a rich source of new biologically active natural products, are considered as important alternative sources of plant metabolites for therapeutic purposes [12]. The potential of endophytic fungi as possible producers of compounds for the treatment of obesity was first shown by Gupta et al. [13-14]. The authors isolated 70 endophytic fungi from the plant *Aegle marmelos*, of which one isolate, classified as *Penicillium*, had an IC₅₀ value of 3.69 mg/ml, comparable to the IC₅₀ of Orlistat (2.73 mg/ml) as a positive control [15-16]. Sarkar et al. [17] showed that two strains isolated from *Citrus lemon* and *Aegle marmelos* inhibited lipase activity by 75% and 83%, respectively. Moreover, the metabolites of the isolate identified as *Pestalotiopsis* sp. contained an inhibitory substance with an activity of 87% and IC₅₀=15.46 µg/µl.

Besides that, complete inhibition of PL by lemon endophyte extracts was demonstrated by Patil et al. [18]. Thus, when screening extracts of 18 endophytes from 6 local plants using the phenol red agar with olive oil method, a complete absence of a yellow halo was revealed under the action of CLL-2 extract and partial inhibition of pancreatic lipase by CLL-1 extract from *Citrus lemon* [18]. At the same time, the efficiency of microorganisms as producers critically

depends on the cultivation parameters [19]. For describing the effect of fermentation parameters on the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites by any microorganism from an increase in the number of substances produced to the appearance of previously unknown natural products, the term "OSMAC" (one strain - many substances) was proposed [20-22]. It was shown that varying such cultivation conditions as medium composition, aeration, temperature, flask shape led to the discovery of new natural products by various fungi and actinomycetes. This is especially evident in endophytes, as there are multifaceted and variable interactions between the endophytic fungus, the host plant, and other endophytes. Although endophytes can grow on conventional nutrient media in the laboratory, even slight changes in in vitro culture conditions can affect the type and range of secondary metabolites produced.

Therefore, for achieving a stable production of the desired secondary metabolite, it is necessary to establish an optimal set of endophyte cultivation parameters.

In our previous studies, a number of endophytic fungi were isolated from local medicinal plants collected in the vicinity of Tashkent (Uzbekistan) and strains of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R isolated from the root of *Viola odorata* and *Fusarium* sp. - AL142R isolated from the root of *Allium filidens* were selected, which have the ability to suppress pancreatic lipase activity by 75% and 73.7%, respectively. In this regard, the aim of this work was to study the effect of the composition of nutrient media and cultivation conditions on the inhibitory activity of secondary metabolites.

Materials and methods. Isolation and cultivation of endophyte fungi was carried out according to Hazline et al. [23] from roots, bulbs, stems, leaves and inflorescences of collected plants. After preliminary treatment with 70% ethanol for 1 minute and washing with sterile water, each plant segment was aseptically chopped into pieces no larger than 0.5 cm and placed on Petri dishes with Czapek-Dox agar medium containing chlortetracycline at a concentration of 50 mg/ml and streptomycin sulfate at a concentration of 250 mg/ml to suppress the growth of bacterial microflora. The dishes were incubated for 7-14 days at a temperature of 28°C. The grown fungal isolates were reseeded on Czapek-Dox medium without antibiotics. In order to accumulate biomass for further extraction and determination of biological activity, the endophytic fungi were subjected to submerged fermentation (SF). For this purpose, the strains were grown in a liquid medium on a shaker at 180 rpm, temperature of 28°C for 7 days. The biomass of the cultures was separated by centrifugation at 6 thousand rpm and stored at + 4°C.

For studying the influence of the cultivation conditions of the selected strains, nutrient media commonly used in the study of the bioactivity of endophytic fungi were used [24-25] (g/l):

Medium 1 (yeast wort): 12% wort - 80 ml, yeast extract - 2.

Medium 2 (soybean-dextrose): soy flour - 10, dextrose - 10.

Medium 3 (potato-dextrose): potato infusion - 100, dextrose - 20.

Medium 4 (meat-peptone): peptone - 5, beef extract - 5, NaCl - 5.

Medium 5 (Czapek-Dox): NaNO₃ - 2, MgSO₄ - 0.5, KCl-0.5, FeSO₄ - 10 mg, KH₂PO₄ - 1.0, sucrose -20 mg, pH 6-6.5.

Extraction of secondary metabolites from endophytic fungal biomass. Extraction of secondary metabolites from endophytic fungal biomass was performed according to Lang et al. with modifications of Hazline et al [23]. For this, 5 g of biomass was homogenized in a Potter homogenizer, transferred to a conical flask, and extracted twice, according to the method, with ethyl acetate, at a rate of 25 ml of extractant per 5 mg of crude homogenized biomass for 24

hours on a circular shaker at room temperature. Then the mixture was filtered through a paper filter (Whatman paper N. 1) and Na₂SO₄ was added at a rate of 40 µg/ml to remove the aqueous layer. Then the mixture was evaporated to dryness on a rotary evaporator and 1 ml of dimethyl sulfoxide was added. The resulting extract was used as a mother liquor and stored at a temperature of +4°C.

Solid-state fermentation. Solid-state fermentation of endophytic fungi was carried out in Petri dishes containing 5.0 g of oat flour moistened to 65% with the following nutrient media: Czapek-Dox, wort-yeast medium, potato-dextrose and enriched nutrient medium with glycerol: (glucose - 11% (w/v), glycerol -16%, MgSO₄ - 0.75%, (NH₂HSO₄ -2.3% (w/v, KH₂PO₄ - 2%, maltose -5%). For sowing, a spore inoculum of 10⁸ 1 ml was used, the strain in a volume of 2.0 ml per 5.0 g of dry substrate. The effect of the duration of solid-state fermentation on the yield of metabolites was monitored in the dynamics of culture growth from 5 to 14 days at a temperature of 28°C.

It is known to everyone that for studying the effect of solid-state fermentation on the yield of metabolites, the cultures were monitored in the dynamics of growth from 5 to 14 days at a temperature of 28°C. To study the influence of the cultivation conditions of the selected strains, we used nutrient media commonly used in the study of the bioactivity of endophytic fungi [25-26] (g/l), and also used an enriched nutrient medium of the following composition: glucose - 11% (w/v), glycerol - 16%, MgSO₄ - 0.75%, (NH₄)₂HSO₄ - 2.3% (w/v), KH₂PO₄ - 2%, maltose - 5%, Ph - 7.5.

All experiments were carried out in triplicate. Quantitative analysis of PL inhibition of endophytic fungal extracts. 50 mg of lipase (“Sigma”, 100 units/ml) were suspended in 10 ml of Tris-HCl buffer containing 2.5 mM Tris and 2.5 mM NaCl, pH 7.4. The solution was shaken vigorously for 15 min and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was collected. Stock solutions of extracts and Xenical were prepared in DMSO with linear concentrations in the range of 1.56–2000 µg/mL or 0.78–1000 µg/mL.

The final reaction mixture consisted of 875 µL of buffer, 100 µL of enzyme, and 20 µL of extract at different stock concentrations, pre-incubated for 5 min at 37°C, followed by the addition of 10 µL of substrate (4-nitrophenyl palmitate at 10 mM in acetonitrile). The amount of DMSO in the final concentration did not exceed 2%. The optical mixture was measured on a spectrophotometer (UV-vis model UV-5100) after 5 minutes at 405 nm. The percentage of inhibition was calculated using the formula: % inhibition = [(Ae-At)/Ae]x100, where Ae is the optical density of the enzyme control (without inhibitor), and at the difference between the optical density of the test sample with and without the substrate. Xenical was used as a comparison drug [26].

Results and discussion. A direct dependence of secondary metabolite synthesis on fermentation conditions was shown in a study of 29 strains of endophytic fungi *Nodulisporium* by Monaghan et al. [27], with a more than 400-fold difference in the concentration of synthesized metabolites observed between different fermentation conditions.

In a study of 760 endophyte strains, Yarbrough et al. [28] found that several different growth conditions are necessary to enhance the production of secondary metabolites. The effect of media composition on secondary synthesis is especially clearly demonstrated in the work of Paranagama et al. [29], where the endophyte *Paraphaeosphaeria quadrisepata* begins to synthesize six new secondary metabolites, even when the water for the medium is changed from

flowing to distilled. When the growing medium of *Chaetomium chiversii* was changed from solid to liquid, it led to the production of radicicol instead of hetochromin A.

As can be seen from the data presented in Fig. 1, during submerged fermentation of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R and *Fusarium* sp. AL142R, the composition of the nutrient medium and the cultivation conditions as a whole significantly affect both the growth of endophytic biomass and the level of secondary metabolites, as well as the PL inhibitory activity of the extracts. It should be noted that the nutrient media used differed quite significantly in composition, as a result of which their effect on the recorded growth parameters and inhibitory activity within each individual strain differed.

The inhibitory activity of the sum of secondary metabolites of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R and *Fusarium* sp. - AL142R was determined under submerged cultivation conditions on five media.

Fig. 1. Effect of cultivation conditions on the growth and inhibitory activity of the extract of secondary metabolites of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R (1) and *Fusarium* sp.-AL142R (2).

When cultivated in submerged conditions, the inhibitory activity of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R metabolites varied from a minimum of 14.9% on medium 3 (potato-dextrose) to a maximum of 75% on medium 5 (Czapek-Doxa), which also showed a high level of secondary metabolite synthesis (42 mg). In general, the data show that the most active inhibitory metabolites are produced during submerged cultivation of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R on Czapek-Doxa medium, where PL inhibition is 75%. It should be noted that the inhibitory activity of Xenical (Orlistat) as a comparison drug under the experimental conditions is 72%. When cultivating *Fusarium* sp.-AL142R, it was also found that cultivation conditions and environments have different effects on biomass growth, secondary metabolite synthesis and their inhibitory activity. The strongest inhibition of PL by *Fusarium* sp.-AL142R extracts was observed during submerged cultivation on medium 1 (wort-yeast) - 61% and on Czapek medium, where the PL inhibition level was 73.7%, which is comparable to the effect of Xenical as a standard (72%). Unlike the endophyte *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R, the yield of dry extract in the *Fusarium* sp.-AL142R strain is generally higher and amounted to 92 mg when grown on Czapek-Dox medium. The level of biomass growth of both strains during submerged cultivation was low on all media, with the exception of medium 3 (potato-dextrose) for the *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R strain (Fig. 1).

In general, the data show that the most active inhibitory metabolites are produced during submerged cultivation of *Aspergillus fischeri* and *Fusarium* sp.-AL142R on Czapek-Dox medium, where PL inhibition is 75% and 73.7%, respectively

The method of solid-phase fermentation of microbial cultures for obtaining target metabolites is more economical compared to traditional cultivation: reducing the humidity of the cultivation substrate, which eliminates the possibility of contamination of the target product; maintaining natural conditions for cultivation; constant access of oxygen during cultivation; use of cost-effective substrates; reducing energy costs; increasing the yield of the target product.

In this regard, in order to optimize the cultivation conditions of endophytes *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R and *Fusarium* sp. - AL₁₄₂R, producing secondary metabolites that inhibit pancreatic lipase activity, cultures were grown on a solid substrate - oat flour moistened with various nutrient media. As a result of solid-phase fermentation on oat flour, it was shown that all the nutrient media used are quite suitable for the development of the mycelium of two strains. In this case, the cultures germinate deeply into the substrate, forming a white mycelium on the surface, which is more pronounced in the strain *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R and *Fusarium* sp. - AL₁₄₂R on the 7th day of growth when the substrate is moistened with Czapek medium and the wort with yeast medium (Fig. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2. Growth of the *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R strain on oat flour moistened with nutrient media: 1. Czapek medium; 2. wort-yeast medium; 3. potato-dextrose medium; 4. enriched nutrient medium.

Fig. 3. Growth of the *Fusarium* sp. - AL142R strain on oat flour moistened with nutrient media: 1. Czapek medium; 2. wort-yeast medium; 3. potato-dextrose medium; 4. enriched nutrient medium.

Since lipase inhibitors are intracellular metabolites, the level of their accumulation in the studied strain depends on the nutrient media used and correlates with the amount of dry extract. Figures 4 and 5 present data reflecting the dynamics of accumulation of metabolites with inhibitory activity during fermentation of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R and *Fusarium* sp. - AL₁₄₂R during TFF on oat flour moistened with various nutrient media.

Certainly, the highest productivity of *Aspergillus fischeri* VO1R and *Fusarium* sp. - AL₁₄₂R is observed on the 9th day of culture growth, while the highest level of inhibitory activity occurs on the 7th day of culture growth. In this case, the maximum PL inhibitory effect of

Aspergillus fischeri VO1R metabolites is observed when moistening oat flour with an enriched nutrient medium (55%), Czapek medium and wort-yeast medium (50%) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Dynamics of accumulation of dry extract and inhibitory activity of the endophytic fungus Aspergillus fischeri VO1R when moistening the substrate with various nutrient media.

Fig. 5. Dynamics of accumulation of dry extract and inhibitory activity of Fusarium sp.-AL142R when moistening the substrate with different nutrient media.

The maximum inhibitory effect of Fusarium sp. - AL₁₄₂R extracts when moistened with Czapek medium and wort-yeast media is slightly higher than that of A fischeri VO1R (54%) and is 58 and 56%, respectively (Fig. 5). The highest accumulation of lipase inhibitors in Fusarium sp. - AL₁₄₂R is observed on the 9th day of culture growth and is 47 mg when moistened with an enriched nutrient medium.

From the data obtained, it follows that solid-phase fermentation is, in principle, a completely suitable method for growing both endophytic strains to obtain sufficient quantities of crude metabolites with significant inhibitory activity. The most active strain was Fusarium sp. - AL₁₄₂R, whose maximum inhibitory effect when moistened with Czapek medium and wort-yeast media is slightly higher than that of A. fischeri VO1R.

Thus, the obtained data show that the cultivation conditions and the composition of the nutrient medium do have a strong effect on the inhibitory activity of endophyte metabolites. This indicates the need for proper selection of media and cultivation conditions for potential producers that can provide a sufficiently high yield of active pancreatic lipase inhibitors.

With regard to the endophytes Aspergillus fischeri VO1R and Fusarium sp.-AL₁₄₂R, it can be concluded that submerged cultivation provides a sufficiently high production of PL

inhibitors with significant activity on the Czapek-Dox medium, amounting to 75% and 73.7% inhibition.

By summarizing it can be suggested that from the totality of the obtained data, it follows that the endophytic fungi *Aspergillus* sp. VO1R, isolated from the root of *Viola odorata* and *Fusarium* sp.-AL142R from the root of *Allium Filidens*, can be considered as promising sources of pancreatic lipase inhibitors for the development of new therapeutic drugs for obesity.

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